

MESO-MECHANICAL INVESTIGATION OF WOVEN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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1 Introduction

Increasing energy costs necessitate efficient lightweight constructions – particularly in the fields of mobility and transport. For these applications, tailorable materials like fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) are gaining more and more importance. The characterization of woven composite structures turned out to be one of the difficulties in the fields of numerical simulation and experimental investigation. The precise prediction of the global material response is only possible by accounting for the internal structure, which can be done at different scales.

A meso-mechanical investigation of woven FRP is not only one of the strongest tools for homogenization of material parameters [1, 2] but also for the study of phenomena caused by their non-uniformity such as stress and strain localization even under global uniform loading [3] as well as damage initiation [4, 5] and propagation in the constituting materials [6, 7]. These numerical analyses build a sound basis for the computationally cheaper macro-mechanical approaches, which are used whenever the mechanical response of large parts is of interest. Therefore scale bridging due to e.g. homogenization procedures must be applied [8].

For the verification of these small scale models, experimental data with a local resolution higher than an individual yarn is necessary [3, 9]. Digital image correlation (DIC) is an advisable tool for high resolution full field strain measurements at the specimen's surface. In the most cases, a second experiment must provide the global data set for the verification of the homogenized response of the meso-model. But the setup must guarantee exactly the same test conditions as for the local experiment, which is hardly possible.

Therefore in this work, an experimental setup is proposed capable of recording both, local and

global, kinematic values. The obtained strain distributions of 4/4 satin weave FRP plates are compared to strain fields of idealized meso-scale representative volume elements (RVE) generated by finite element calculations under in-plane loading conditions using periodic boundary conditions with varying fiber orientations at the same deformation state. Furthermore, the experimentally obtained global recordings and homogenized stress strain response of the meso-scale analysis are compared.

2 Experiments

2.1 Setup

The test setup including a 'Zwick Z100' testing machine and an 'Aramis M4' DIC system is shown in Figure 1.

This setup allows for synchronized recording of force as well as local and global displacement fields/values. The Zwick's load cell signal as well as the global displacement signals of the (external) DIC system are recorded using the control software 'TestXpert II' of Zwick/Roell. Analog online signal transfer – e.g. length change, etc. measured by the DIC system – from Aramis to the testing machines software is realized by the integration of a 'HBM Spider 8' measuring amplifier. Time, force, cross beam displacement and nominal strain are generated by Zwick's (internal) sensors. Unfortunately, the kinematic quantities of the crossbar displacement are insufficient, since the deformation of the load frame and the gliding of the grippers are added to the pure elongation of the specimen. To overcome this problem, an external displacement measurement system is applied. The Aramis system supports the observation of up to ten points at the specimens' surface in the real-time-sensor (rts) mode, while simultaneously saving images for the later analysis of the whole strain field. All displacement values are mapped online to a coordinate system that is

parallel to the testing machine's force axis. Coded markers attached to a stiff frame at the static (upper) jaw serve as fixed points to span up the virtual coordinate system within the Aramis software.

While testing, the DIC system can be seen as an optical extensometer. The sampling rate of the global strain values must be very high, since the testing machine is controlled by the global length change. On the other hand, the bandwidth to stream the live images of the two cameras limits the sampling rate initially to 60 Hz. To increase the sampling rate to 120 Hz, only the upper half of the cameras CCD chip is used, and thus the amount of data that is transferred from the cameras to the computer is halved. Thereby the height of the image is halved, whereas the width remains the same. Since the specimens are longer than wider, the cameras were turned by 90° to use the image width to capture the specimen's length. Thereby, there is no need to increase the distance between the camera and the testing object, preserving the accuracy of the setup.

Assuming a homogeneous deformation state at the center of the specimen, only two points at the longitudinal axis of the specimen are needed to determine 'global' length change and strain values. By observing two additional points in transversal direction, also global Poisson ratio values were recorded. The initial distance between the points in longitudinal direction was about 16 mm, which is the length of the RVE in this weave. The positions of the measuring points are shown in Figure 2. In this series, four woven carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CRP) plates for varying fiber angles from 0° to 90° in 15° increments were tested.

2.2 Specimen

Each FRP plate consisted of two layers of a 4/4 satin weave impregnated with epoxy resin. The manufacturer's specification of the investigated material is 'ACG CF0500' 3k carbon fiber weave. Water jet cutting was used for manufacturing in order to avoid fiber and matrix damage at the plate's sides. Cap strips, made of the specimen's material, applied at the plate ends prevented fiber damage during clamping and testing. Furthermore, a random pattern was sprayed at one of the specimen sides, which is needed for the DIC measurements. Titanium dioxide powder spray was used for the white base coat while graphite spray sparkles

induced the contrast. Invalid tests, e.g. when slippage and/or rupture of the cap strips was detected, were discarded. The specimen's geometry and dimensions are given in Figure 3 and Table 1.

The total force versus global Aramis displacement of one exemplary testing of each fiber orientation is shown in Figure 4.

3 Finite element simulations

A meso-scale RVE of a woven FRP ply consists generally of two distinct materials. First, there is the so-called yarn part, and second there is the surrounding pure matrix region. The yarn part has similar properties to a unidirectional (UD) FRP ply since within the yarn all the fibers are aligned in the same direction. Yarns in different directions imply the different fiber directions apparent in woven structures. The geometry of the internal structure differentiating the yarns from the matrix is shown in Figure 5. The geometry of the yarn is precisely described in [9]. In figure 5, one can clearly see the crimped regions of the yarns. Since every yarn has a different position of the crimp region, every yarn has its own local material coordinate system ensuring the proper definition of the directions of the transversal isotropic material behavior, see Figure 6. In contrast, there is no evidence of local material coordinates for the isotropic matrix material.

A complete 8 x 8 yarns RVE of the weave is modeled. In this simulation, a total number of about 1.3 million elements and 2.6 million nodes represent the behavior of a real FRP piece of about 16 mm x 16 mm x 0.4 mm. Hexahedral elements occupy the fibrous parts, the surrounding matrix is discretized with tetrahedral elements.

Using periodic boundary conditions (PBC) and tensile as well as shear in-plane loading, virtually the situation of the ply during the experiments is represented. Equation constraints were used to model the PBC in Abaqus. In the following, the equations are summarized.

Faces:

$$u_i^1 - u_i^3 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u_i^2 - u_i^4 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$u_i^6 - u_i^5 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p] \quad (15)$$

Vertices:

$$u_i^3 - u_i^5 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$u_i^2 - u_i^8 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 + c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$u_i^7 - u_i^1 + a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$u_i^4 - u_i^6 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 + b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (7)$$

The widely used yield criterion $\Phi(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_c, \sigma_t)$, proposed by Tschoegl [10], and a non-associative plastic flow potential $\psi(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \alpha)$ tackle the necessity of different yield strengths in tensile and compressive direction as well as the pressure dependency of the material

$$\Phi(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \sigma_c, \sigma_t) = 6J_2 + 2I_1(\sigma_c - \sigma_t) - 2\sigma_c \sigma_t \quad (16)$$

Edges:

$$u_i^2 - u_i^4 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$u_i^1 - u_i^3 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 + b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$u_i^6 - u_i^8 + a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$u_i^5 - u_i^7 - a \varepsilon_{i1}^0 + c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$u_i^{11} - u_i^9 - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 - c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$u_i^{10} - u_i^{12} - b \varepsilon_{i2}^0 + c \varepsilon_{i3}^0 = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \alpha) = 3J_2 + \frac{1}{9}\alpha I_1^2 \quad (17)$$

where σ_c, σ_t are the yield strengths in compressive and tensile direction, respectively. $J_2 = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^D : \boldsymbol{\sigma}^D$ is the second invariant of the deviatoric stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^D$ and $I_1 = tr(\boldsymbol{\sigma})$ is the first invariant of the stress tensor. For the correct definition of the volumetric plastic flow, the material parameter $\alpha = \frac{9}{2} \frac{1-2\nu_p}{1+\nu_p}$ with ν_p being the plastic Poisson's ratio, is defined. Furthermore, the evolution of the plastic and equivalent plastic strain is defined as

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{eq}^p = \sqrt{k \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p} \quad (19)$$

Here the index $i = 1, 2, 3$ indicates the direction and the superscript corresponds to the number of the face, edge or vertex as shown in Figure 7. a, b and c are the lengths of the RVE in the 1, 2 and 3 direction, respectively. ε_{ij}^0 are the components of the far field strain tensor.

respectively. The constant $k = \frac{1}{1+2\nu_p}$ ensures the proper definition of the equivalent plastic strain under uniaxial tension. The tensile and compressive yield strength defining the yield criterion are provided by two Voce-type hardening laws

4 Constitutive modeling

4.1 Matrix material

In this simulation, an elasto-plastic behavior for the neat matrix regions is taken into account. Until now, no damage phenomena contribute to the dissipative potential.

Starting point is the additive decomposition of the total strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ into its elastic part $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ and its plastic part $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p$.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \quad (14)$$

Thus, the constitutive law can be written as

$$\sigma_t = Q_t \left(1 - e^{\eta_t \varepsilon_{eq}^p}\right) + \sigma_{t0} \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_c = Q_c \left(1 - e^{\eta_c \varepsilon_{eq}^p}\right) + \sigma_{c0} \quad (21)$$

where σ_{t0}, σ_{c0} are the initial yield strengths in tension and compression, and Q_t, Q_c, η_t and η_c denote material parameters defining the hardening.

An elastic predictor – plastic corrector return mapping algorithm was implemented in the

commercial finite element software Abaqus using the UMAT subroutine.

Experimental results of neat epoxy resin performed by Fiedler [5] where the basis of the parameter fit. Figure 8 shows the agreement of the numerical and experimental results. The material parameters used to achieve these results are shown in Table 2.

4.2 Yarn (UD) material

The yarn part has similar properties to pure UD FRP. Here, only a linear elastic, transversal isotropic material model is used to represent the reinforcement on the meso-scale. To obtain the elastic properties, a micro RVE with hexagonal packing of the perfectly aligned fibers and fiber volume fraction of 60% was set up, see Figure 9. At the micro-scale, only homogeneous linear elastic material models with different material parameters for the fiber and the matrix part (parameters see Table 3) were taken into account.

Using periodicity conditions, six individual calculations were performed with varying far field strain components of 1% for any of the six components of the far field strain tensor. By calculating the volume averaged stresses, one can obtain the individual components of the material tangent operator

$$\hat{C}_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \frac{\hat{\sigma}_i}{\hat{\epsilon}_j^0} dV \quad (22)$$

where $i, j = 1, \dots, 6$, \hat{C}_{ij} and $\hat{\sigma}_i$ are the components of the material tangent and the stress, respectively, and $\hat{\epsilon}_j^0$ is the applied far field strain component. The hat ($\hat{\cdot}$) indicates Voigt notation.

Now one can obtain the homogenized elastic engineering constants of the UD material. The parameters are shown in Table 4.

5 Comparisons and discussion

For the validation of the model, the experimentally and numerically obtained strain field of the RVE as well as the global experimentally obtained values versus the evolution of the numerically homogenized stress strain response is shown. Here only the results of the 0°/90° and 45°/135° fiber orientations are discussed.

In Figures 10 and 11, the local strain field for ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} of the 0°/90° specimen under tensile loading is presented. A correlation of the reasonable strain fields can be observed. In this scenario, the total strain is very low, since fracture occurred at about 1,7%. For this setup, the total material response can be seen as linear elastic, as will be shown later, which is also a reason for the good correspondence.

Figures 12 and 13 show the strain field for ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} for the 45°/135° fiber orientation. At this point of the deformation state, the elastic region is left behind. The correlation can still be observed, but as soon as larger deformations come into picture, localization effects not only due to plasticity, but also due to voids, fiber misalignment, matrix breakage as well as damage within the yarns play an important role. This has a massive negative effect to the correlation of the strain fields observed. A micro CT analysis of the weave also shows many of the defects, see Figure 14.

The global values causing these deformations are comparative values as well. In Figure 15, the nearly linear response of the numerically homogenized stress field is plotted against the far field strain value. Additionally, the experimentally obtained engineering stress values are plotted against the global longitudinal strain observed from the DIC system. A slight increase of the experimental values at strains above 0.8% can be observed. This can be caused by the straightening of the yarns under tensile loading. The numerical response of the global material behavior correlates with the experiments.

Furthermore, the shear stresses over shear strains are calculated, and plotted in Figure 16. Also in this setup, the elastic response of both, simulation and experiment correlate. Beyond this point, the numerical predictions do not meet the experimentally observed response. The same reasons already mentioned above for the decorrelation of the local strain field fit here. The breakage of the matrix nest and the resulting loss of stiffness as well as the fiber matrix debonding in the yarn part play a major role here.

6 Conclusions

An experimental setup capable of recording local as well as global kinematic quantities is proposed. This setup provides the exact values to

validate meso-mechanical approaches for the simulation of woven FRP structures. Furthermore, a meso-scale RVE of a 4/4 satin weave was set up for the numerical analysis of the weave. In this simulation a non-associative plastic material formulation was used to model the matrix region. The transversal isotropic parameters for the yarn part were obtained by the homogenization of an ideal hexagonal packing of an unidirectional RVE. Periodicity conditions were applied to represent the conditions of the ply during the experiment. Numerically and experimentally obtained stress fields as well as the homogenized and global stress strain response of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $45^\circ/135^\circ$ fiber orientations were compared. The numerical and experimental response at small deformations correlate. At large deformations, particularly at large shear strains, the necessity of a damage formulation for the yarn and the matrix material is obvious.

Parameter	Value
s	300.0 mm
l	200.0 mm
w	40.0 mm
t	0.8 mm

Tab.1. Specification of the specimen's geometry parameters

Property	Value
K	3600.0 MPa
G	1350.0 MPa
ν_p	0.32
Q_t	67.0
η_t	82.0
σ_{t0}	29.0 MPa
Q_c	58.0
η_c	75.0
σ_{c0}	67.0 MPa

Tab.2. Material parameters for the matrix material in meso-scale RVE

	E	ν
Matrix	241 GPa	0.2
Fiber	3.12 GPa	0.38

Tab.3. Material parameters used in micro RVE

Property	Value
E_1	145.53 GPa
$E_2 = E_3$	12.99 GPa
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	4.35 GPa
G_{23}	4.40 GPa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.26
ν_{23}	0.47

Tab.4. Homogenized transversal isotropic material parameters for the yarn part

Fig.1. Experimental setup

Fig.2. Positions of measuring points for rts mode

Fig.3. Geometry of specimen

Fig.4. Force vs. global displacement of different fiber orientations

Fig.8. Comparison of numerical and experimental results of the matrix material

Fig.5. Internal structure of RVE

Fig.6. Detail of the crimp region showing the local material coordinate system

Fig.9. Hexagonal package micro RVE

Fig.7. Definition of the face, vertex and edge numbering

Fig.10. ϵ_{11} experiment (l) and simulation (r) $0^\circ/90^\circ$

Fig.11. ϵ_{22} experiment (l) and simulation (r) $0^\circ/90^\circ$

Fig.12. ϵ_{11} experiment (l) and simulation (r) $45^\circ/135^\circ$

Fig.13. ϵ_{22} experiment (l) and simulation (r) $45^\circ/135^\circ$

Fig.14. Micro CT image of FRP weave showing voids

Fig.15. Numerically and experimentally obtained global stress strain curve of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ ply

Fig.16. Numerically and experimentally obtained global stress strain curve of $45^\circ/135^\circ$ ply

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